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A Proactive Approach to the Recovery and Recycling of Photovoltaic Modules

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D10.1: LCA, LCC, SLCA and CBM baselines report

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Table of contents

1.	Executive summary	1
2.	Planned criteria	2
3.	Lifecycle assessment (LCA)	3
3.1	Introduction	3
3.2	Goal and scope definition	4
3.2.1	Goal of the Study	4
3.2.2	Scope of the Study	5
3.3	Lifecycle inventory (LCI) analysis	5
3.3.1	Cradle-to-gate processes	5
3.3.2	Downstream processes.....	6
3.4	Lifecycle impact assessment (LCIA)	7
3.4.1	7N solar grade Si	9
3.4.2	PV modules	15
3.5	Conclusion	22
4.	Lifecycle costing (LCC)	24
4.1	Introduction	24
4.2	Methodology	24
4.3	Cost breakdown.....	24
4.4	Conclusion	25
5.	Social lifecycle assessment (S-LCA)	27
5.1	Introduction	27
5.2	Goal and Scope Definition	27
5.3	Method	28
5.4	Social lifecycle inventory (S-LCI): Stakeholder Risks and Social Hotspots	29
5.5	Impact Assessment (S-LCIA): Social Risk Scoring and Hotspot Evaluation	1
5.5.1	Aggregated social risk scores.....	1
5.5.2	Life cycle stage and stakeholder indicators.....	3
5.5.3	Material specific insights	1
5.6	Social impact hotspots and insights.....	2
5.6.1	Severe upstream risks.....	2
5.6.2	Moderate downstream and end-of-life risks.....	3
5.6.3	Positive societal contributions.....	3
5.6.4	System-wide governance and value chain vulnerabilities.....	3
5.6.5	Implications for strategy.....	3

6.	Circular business model baseline- Management of Materials Throughout Silicon Photovoltaic (Si-PV) Lifecycles.....	4
6.1	Introduction.....	4
6.2	Method.....	4
6.3	PV Market analysis.....	5
6.4	Materials markets.....	6
6.4.1	Silver (Ag).....	7
6.4.2	Silicon (Si).....	7
6.4.3	Copper.....	8
6.4.4	Aluminium.....	8
6.4.5	Secondary sources.....	9
6.5	Current Business Models and Material Flow for EoL PV.....	10
6.5.1	Linear Disposal and Downcycling Models.....	10
6.5.2	Upcycling and High-Value Recycling.....	11
6.6	Emerging Multi-Revenue Business Models.....	12
6.7	Centralized and decentralized recycling.....	12
6.8	Policy and Regulatory Landscape.....	13
6.9	Baseline Summary.....	13
7.	Conclusion.....	14
8.	References.....	15
9.	Annex 1 – Lifecycle inventory of cradle to gate processes.....	17
10.	Annex 2 – SLCA supporting information.....	29

List of figures

Figure 1 Production processes for Si wafers from silica raw materials with the potential role of apollo innovations to supply 7n silicon for ingot production	4
Figure 2 Cradle-to-grave system boundary for mono-Si PERC photovoltaic modules LCA.....	5
Figure 3 Reiling mechanical recycling process ⁵	7
Figure 4 Contributions to environmental impacts of 7N solar grade silicon	12
Figure 5 Contributions to environmental impacts of MG-Si	15
Figure 6 Contributions to total cradle to grave impacts of Solar PV modules from lifecycle stages.	18
Figure 7 Contributions to module cradle to gate impacts	21
Figure 8 Breakdown of environmental impacts across categories for PERC cell production	22
Figure 9 Global PV market data ³⁷	5
Figure 10 Projected Global PV waste by region ¹⁵	6
Figure 11 PV waste volumes predicted in Europe.....	6
Figure 12 Market data for silver supply, demand and value ³⁹	7
Figure 13 Projected demand for Si.....	8
Figure 14 Market data for copper ^{38,40,41}	8
Figure 15 Aluminium market analysis data ⁴²	9
Figure 16 Major secondary sources of PV materials.....	10
Figure 17 Material recovery outcome from downcycling of PV modules.....	11
Figure 18 Materials recovery outcomes from upcycling of PV modules	11

List of tables

Table 1 Characteristics of FuturaSun mono-facial PERC module – FU 460 M Silk Pro ²	6
Table 2 Description of ReCiPe midpoint (hierarchist) LCIA method impact categories.....	9
Table 3 Per kg Cradle to gate environmental impacts of 7N solar grade silicon	11
Table 4 Per kg impacts of MG-silicon from raw materials	14
Table 5 Cradle-to-grave environmetal impacts of 460W PERC PV module	17
Table 6 Cradle to gate impacts of PV module	20
Table 7 Published cradle-to-gate GWP values for mono-Si PV modules	20
Table 8 Cost summary estimate for lifetime costs of PV per Wp of installed capacity	25
Table 9 Life Cycle Inventory of Key Materials and Associated Social Risks by Stakeholder Group.....	1
Table 10 Aggregated social risk scores by stakeholder group and PV lifecycle stage (Colour codes indicate severity of risk).....	3
Table 11 Detailed Social Indicator Scoring by Stakeholder group	1

Table 12 Material-Specific Indicator Scores and Stakeholder Risks.....	2
Table 13 Industrial partners engaged	4
Table 14 LCI data for MG-Si production.....	17
Table 15 LCI data for 7N grade Si production	18
Table 16 LCI for Cz process ingot production.....	19
Table 17 LCI for wafer production process	20
Table 18 LCI for PERC Cell production.....	21
Table 19 LCI for Silver Metallization paste for frontside of PERC cells	23
Table 20 LCI for silver metallization paste for rear side of PERC cells	24
Table 21 LCI for aluminium metallization paste.....	24
Table 22 LCI for Trimethyl aluminium (TMA).....	25
Table 23 LCI for Silane production	25
Table 24 LCI for PERC PV module production	26
Table 25 LCI for distribution of PV module to Europe from China.....	27
Table 26 LCI for transport of Waste PV module from site of use to recycling plant via collection facility.....	27
Table 27 LCI for recycling of PERC module.....	28
Table 28 Cradle-to-grave LCI for PERC module manufactured in china and transported for use and recycling in Europe	28
Table 29 Social impact indicators for stakeholder groups	29

Terms, definitions and abbreviated terms

BoS	Balance of System
C-Si	Crystalline Silicon
EE	Embodied Energy
EoL	End-of-Life
EPBT	Energy Payback Time
EU	European Union
FiT	Feed-in Tariff
GHG	Greenhouse Gas
GWP	Global Warming Potential
IEA	International Energy Agency
IRENA	International Renewable Energy Agency
LCC	Lifecycle Costing
LCA	Lifecycle Assessment
NREL	National Renewable Energy Laboratory
O&M	Operations and Maintenance
PERC	Passivated Emitter and Rear Cell
PV	Photovoltaic
PVPS	Photovoltaic Power Systems Programme
S-LCA	Social Lifecycle Assessment
Si	Silicon
Si-PV	Silicon Photovoltaic

WEEE Waste Electrical and Electronic Equipment

Wp Watt Peak

1. Executive summary

This report establishes comprehensive environmental, economic, and social baselines for silicon photovoltaic (Si-PV) modules, providing a foundation for evaluating future circular innovations proposed within the APOLLO project. The lifecycle assessment (LCA) demonstrates that Si-PV modules, while offering significant climate mitigation benefits through renewable electricity generation, involve considerable environmental impacts concentrated in silicon production and module manufacturing stages. The baseline global warming potential (GWP) per watt-peak (Wp) is estimated at 0.417 kgCO₂eq/Wp, reflecting recent advancements in efficiency and production processes. The lifecycle cost (LCC) analysis confirms that current Si-PV technologies remain cost-effective, with module procurement and balance-of-system components dominating costs. Though end-of-life (EoL) costs are relatively low, emerging policy frameworks and recycling innovations may shift future economic dynamics, highlighting opportunities for cost reductions via design improvements and enhanced material recovery. The social lifecycle assessment (S-LCA) reveals critical social risks concentrated upstream in the supply chain, particularly related to forced and child labour, gender inequality, and community displacement in mining regions. Downstream stages, including use and recycling, exhibit lower risks and can provide social co-benefits such as job creation and enhanced energy access. The analysis of current business models for Si-PV materials management shows that linear disposal and low-value downcycling dominate today's practices. While emerging multi-revenue and high-value recycling models show promise, they remain at an early stage and face economic and regulatory hurdles. The integrated baseline presented in this report highlights both the progress and challenges facing the Si-PV sector. By establishing clear benchmarks for environmental, economic, and social dimensions, this report supports the development and future assessment of APOLLO's innovative circular business models and technological pathways. Ultimately, it provides a critical tool for guiding policy, industry practices, and research strategies toward a more sustainable and circular solar energy future.

2. Planned criteria

This report outlines research conducted for APOLLO work package 10 (WP10) i.e. Baseline and Priorities: Environmental and Circular Business Modelling. To assess the sustainability advantages associated with processes and business models resulting from innovations developed under APOLLO (i.e. during WP11 to follow), baseline scenarios for Si-PV module lifecycles and the flow of contained materials through production, use and EoL management of modules were established. Environmental and social impacts and economic costs associated with these PV module lifecycles were assessed. This was done in 4 tasks:

Task 10.1 Lifecycle assessment (LCA) baseline conducted by Swansea University (SU) – a cradle to grave LCA of monocrystalline-Si PERC modules

Task 10.2 Lifecycle cost (LCC) baseline conducted by EDP CNET (EDP) – which establishes a cost baseline for lifecycle management of PV modules

Task 10.3 Social lifecycle assessment (SLCA) baseline conducted by SU – a cradle to grave social lifecycle assessment for PV modules.

Task 10.4 Circular business model baseline (EDP) – in which existing business models governing flows of materials throughout PV lifecycles was established through engagement with commercial partners and market research.

3. Lifecycle assessment (LCA)

3.1 Introduction

Si-PV technologies have undergone considerable innovation since the technology first emerged resulting in increasingly efficient solar cells PV modules with a plethora of cell technologies and production approaches. Environmental efficiencies in production have increased considerably as production has scaled greatly in recent years and Si-PV progresses along its technological learning curve. To benchmark the environmental impact of Si-PV modules throughout its lifecycles, it is necessary to establish which of the numerous Si-PV technologies available is most representative of PV on the market today, which production processes are most typical, and what module specifications are typical today. It is also necessary to establish the locations of production, use and disposal as well as disposal processes used to create a suitable baseline model.

Today >90% of 7N polysilicon feedstock for Si-PV wafer production is produced via the Siemens process, and this approach is expected to remain the dominant one for years to come despite the emergence of alternative technologies such as fluidized bed reactors (Figure 1). Today monocrystalline Si (mono-Si) PV dominates the market with multicrystalline PV having almost disappeared because of higher cell efficiencies exhibited of mono-Si and the rapidly reducing cost of producing mono-Si cells. Mono-Si wafers are cut from mono-Si ingots produced from 7N poly-Si via the Czochralski (Cz) process. China dominates production of solar grade Si, as well as PV wafers, cells and modules. Passivated emitter and rear cells (PERC) are now the dominant cell technology in PV modules and are the system of choice for utility scale PV. Typical modules now exceed 21% efficiency, have an area of approximately 2 m², and exceed 400 Wp power generation. Typical end-of-life (EoL) processes vary according to geography along with regulation and legislation governing EoL treatment and the subsequent economics of landfilling, incineration and recycling (as discussed in later chapters). As an initial baseline, we consider that modules are manufactured in China and transported for use in Europe, where they are subsequently recycled at end-of-life (EoL).

Here we conduct a lifecycle assessment of this baseline PV module across its entire lifecycle including the impact of producing 7N grade silicon from which mono-Si ingots, wafers and cells are manufactured. This is important to understand the environmental impacts associated with PV modules and to form a baseline against which future strategies for production and recycling can be considered in order to evaluate the environmental advantages associated with innovation in PV lifecycles, and provide data which can inform policy and research strategies going forward.

FIGURE 1 PRODUCTION PROCESSES FOR SI WAFERS FROM SILICA RAW MATERIALS WITH THE POTENTIAL ROLE OF APOLLO INNOVATIONS TO SUPPLY 7N SILICON FOR INGOT PRODUCTION

3.2 Goal and scope definition

Cradle-to-Grave LCA per Wp of Mono-Si PERC PV module with foreground cradle-to-gate 7N Si production.

3.2.1 Goal of the Study

Objective: To quantify the cradle-to-grave environmental impacts per watt-peak (Wp) of mono-crystalline silicon PERC photovoltaic modules produced in China and used and recycled in Europe, including a detailed foreground cradle-to-gate model of 7N-grade silicon production using the Siemens process.

Applications

- Determination of environmental benefits associated with circular supply of materials into production and new approaches to recycling resulting from APOLLO
- Decision support for greener production, sourcing, and design
- Input for prospective policy and carbon footprint reporting

Intended audience: PV manufacturers, sustainability professionals, researchers, policy advisors

Comparative assertions: The study may support comparisons (e.g., regional production scenarios, PERC vs TOPCon), but must undergo critical review if used for public disclosure per ISO 14044.

3.2.2 Scope of the Study

Functional Unit: 1 Wp of PV capacity, based on a typical mono-Si PERC module

System boundary: Figure 2

FIGURE 2 CRADLE-TO-GRAVE SYSTEM BOUNDARY FOR MONO-SI PERC PHOTOVOLTAIC MODULES LCA

3.3 Lifecycle inventory (LCI) analysis

3.3.1 Cradle-to-gate processes

The supply chain of the PERC cell PV modules includes polycrystalline purification via the Siemens process, the crystallization process to produce mono-Si ingots via the Cz process and wafering. Wafers are further processed into PERC cells, which are then assembled into PV modules. Data published by *Frischknecht et al.* is used for LCI for production stages up to wafering.¹ Data published by *Danelli et al.* is used for the LCI for

cell fabrication and module assembly.² The module is therefore assumed to be a FuturaSun mono-facial PERC module (FU 460 M Silk Pro), produced in Jiangsu China with the characteristics given in Table 1. Lifecycle inventories for each step in the production process are given in Annex 1 (Table 14 to Table 24). Numerous LCI items in the aforementioned published LCIs were not available in LCI databases and had to be modelled. was modelled based upon a patented process for it’s production The LCI for production of trimethyl aluminium (TMA) is based upon the reaction of methyl chloride with aluminium to form an intermediate which subsequently reacts with sodium to yield TMA (Table 22).³ Compressed air was modelled as the energy required to compress it t approximately 7 bar consuming 0.11 kWh of electricity per Nm³.

TABLE 1 CHARACTERISTICS OF FUTURASUN MONO-FACIAL PERC MODULE – FU 460 M SILK PRO²

Module type	Mono-Si PV with PERC cells
Dimensions	2,094 x 1,038 x 35 mm
Weight	23.6 kg
Module power (Pmax)	460 W
Module Efficiency	21.16%
Number of cells	144 half-cut M6 cells
Performance guarantee	25 years

3.3.2 Downstream processes

Transport to Europe for use is assumed to involve 300 km of transport via truck from factory to port, 20,000 km of intercontinental shipping to Europe (Rotterdam), followed by a further 800 km of inland transport by truck for installation. LCI data used for distribution is given in Table 25. Installation and use was excluded from the system boundaries due to its negligible contribution to the overall life cycle impacts of the PV module. Previous studies indicate that installation accounts for less than 1–2% of environmental impacts when compared to module production and energy generation over the system lifetime.^{1,2,4} EoL treatment is modelled as mechanical recycling which is still the benchmark in Europe and optimized for costs, capacity, and output though frequently results in downgrading of material quality. Reiling’s improved, mechanical process for silicon-based modules represents a fully commercial 10,000 t/year best available technology that sets a benchmark for maturity, cost, and low energy consumption. However, it does not allow recovery of silicon and silver. Recycling here is modelled using LCI data for Reiling’s process (Figure 3).⁵ Recovered materials from PV panel recycling were modelled separately where possible (glass cullet, plastic waste, and metal scrap). Residual mixed fractions were assumed to be sent to mechanical sorting or thermal treatment. Where detailed treatment data was unavailable, mixed waste fractions were conservatively modelled as incinerated or landfilled residual waste.

FIGURE 3 REILING MECHANICAL RECYCLING PROCESS ⁵

3.4 Lifecycle impact assessment (LCIA)

LCIA was conducted using Simapro v9.6 with and the ReCiPe midpoint (hierarchist) impact assessment method This quantifies environmental impacts in the categories shown in

Table 2 with an explanation of the indicator for each impact category and the units of impact. The ecoinvent version 3.10 database cut-off system model was used as the background database for all processes including photovoltaic (PV) panel production, transport, and end-of-life treatment.

TABLE 2 DESCRIPTION OF ReCiPe MIDPOINT (HIERARCHIST) LCIA METHOD IMPACT CATEGORIES

<i>Impact Category</i>	<i>Indicator Description</i>	<i>Unit</i>
<i>Climate Change</i>	<i>Global warming potential (100-year horizon)</i>	<i>kg CO₂ eq</i>
<i>Ozone Depletion</i>	<i>Depletion of the stratospheric ozone layer</i>	<i>kg CFC-11 eq</i>
<i>Terrestrial Acidification</i>	<i>Soil and water acidification from air pollution</i>	<i>kg SO₂ eq</i>
<i>Freshwater Eutrophication</i>	<i>Nutrient enrichment of freshwater</i>	<i>kg P eq</i>
<i>Marine Eutrophication</i>	<i>Nutrient enrichment of marine environments</i>	<i>kg N eq</i>
<i>Human Toxicity</i>	<i>Human exposure to toxic substances</i>	<i>kg 1,4-DCB eq</i>
<i>Photochemical Oxidant Formation</i>	<i>Formation of ozone at ground level</i>	<i>kg NMVOC eq</i>
<i>Particulate Matter Formation</i>	<i>Health effects from particulate matter</i>	<i>kg PM_{2.5} eq</i>
<i>Terrestrial Ecotoxicity</i>	<i>Toxic impacts on land ecosystems</i>	<i>kg 1,4-DCB eq</i>
<i>Freshwater Ecotoxicity</i>	<i>Toxic impacts on freshwater ecosystems</i>	<i>kg 1,4-DCB eq</i>
<i>Marine Ecotoxicity</i>	<i>Toxic impacts on marine ecosystems</i>	<i>kg 1,4-DCB eq</i>
<i>Ionising Radiation (human health)</i>	<i>Exposure to radioactive substances</i>	<i>kBq Co-60 eq</i>
<i>Agricultural Land Occupation</i>	<i>Use of agricultural land over time</i>	<i>m²a</i>
<i>Urban Land Occupation</i>	<i>Use of urban land over time</i>	<i>m²a</i>
<i>Natural Land Transformation</i>	<i>Conversion of natural land</i>	<i>m²</i>
<i>Water Depletion</i>	<i>Use of freshwater resources</i>	<i>m³</i>
<i>Metal Depletion</i>	<i>Extraction of metal ores</i>	<i>kg Cu eq</i>
<i>Fossil Resource Scarcity</i>	<i>Depletion of fossil energy resources</i>	<i>kg oil eq</i>

3.4.1 7N solar grade Si

The environmental impacts of producing 1 kg of 7N solar grade silicon are shown in

Table 3 and the overall contributions towards total impacts in each category of each process input and output are shown in Figure 4. The global warming potential (GWP) is 22.6 kgCO₂eq/kg of 7N solar grade Si. The impacts of MG-Si dominate impacts in all categories contributing 80% to overall GWP. HCl is the next most significant contributor to impacts across all categories.

TABLE 3 PER KG CRADLE TO GATE ENVIRONMENTAL IMPACTS OF 7N SOLAR GRADE SILICON

Impact category	Unit	Total
Global warming	kg CO ₂ eq	2.26E+01
Stratospheric ozone depletion	kg CFC11 eq	6.22E-06
Ionizing radiation	kBq Co-60 eq	6.72E-01
Ozone formation, Human health	kg NO _x eq	5.66E-02
Fine particulate matter formation	kg PM2.5 eq	3.16E-02
Ozone formation, Terrestrial ecosystems	kg NO _x eq	5.77E-02
Terrestrial acidification	kg SO ₂ eq	7.59E-02
Freshwater eutrophication	kg P eq	7.57E-03
Marine eutrophication	kg N eq	4.44E-04
Terrestrial ecotoxicity	kg 1,4-DCB	1.24E+03
Freshwater ecotoxicity	kg 1,4-DCB	5.24E-01
Marine ecotoxicity	kg 1,4-DCB	3.13E+00
Human carcinogenic toxicity	kg 1,4-DCB	2.26E+00
Human non-carcinogenic toxicity	kg 1,4-DCB	1.55E+01
Land use	m ² a crop eq	6.44E-01
Mineral resource scarcity	kg Cu eq	4.44E-02
Fossil resource scarcity	kg oil eq	4.99E+00
Water consumption	m ³	7.75E-02

FIGURE 4 CONTRIBUTIONS TO ENVIRONMENTAL IMPACTS OF 7N SOLAR GRADE SILICON

MG-Si has a GWP of 16.1 kgCO₂eq/kg (

Table 4), with the 67% of this impact resulting from electricity consumed for to power this high temperature carbothermic reduction process, 22% from process emissions of the greenhouse gas reaction products, and coke which is the process reductant and itself is produced in high temperature pyrolysis of coke accounts for 6% of the rest (Figure 5). The high embodied impacts in MG-Si therefore carry over into 7N Si.

TABLE 4 PER KG IMPACTS OF MG-SILICON FROM RAW MATERIALS

Impact category	Unit	Total
Global warming	kg CO ₂ eq	16.0749114
Stratospheric ozone depletion	kg CFC11 eq	3.68378E-06
Ionizing radiation	kBq Co-60 eq	0.449813633
Ozone formation, Human health	kg NOx eq	0.042878858
Fine particulate matter formation	kg PM2.5 eq	0.023125184
Ozone formation, Terrestrial ecosystems	kg NOx eq	0.043505457
Terrestrial acidification	kg SO ₂ eq	0.056802397
Freshwater eutrophication	kg P eq	0.005368952
Marine eutrophication	kg N eq	0.000220367
Terrestrial ecotoxicity	kg 1,4-DCB	1071.592975
Freshwater ecotoxicity	kg 1,4-DCB	0.286321864
Marine ecotoxicity	kg 1,4-DCB	2.521127511
Human carcinogenic toxicity	kg 1,4-DCB	1.445148702
Human non-carcinogenic toxicity	kg 1,4-DCB	9.706077978
Land use	m ² a crop eq	0.497851529
Mineral resource scarcity	kg Cu eq	0.027208821
Fossil resource scarcity	kg oil eq	3.238401649
Water consumption	m ³	0.039684588

FIGURE 5 CONTRIBUTIONS TO ENVIRONMENTAL IMPACTS OF MG-Si

3.4.2 PV modules

The cradle-to-grave environmental impacts of the assessed modules produced in China and distributed to Europe for use and recycling at EoL are shown in

Table 5. The GWP for the PV module is found to be 192 kgCO₂eq and 0.417 kgCO₂eq/Wp. Impacts are dominated by module production. In all impact categories cradle to gate impacts of modules contribute 80-99% in all categories except freshwater and marine ecotoxicity which for which EoL treatment contributes approximately 70% of total impact (Figure 6). Distribution most significantly impacts ozone formation, terrestrial acidification, and eutrophication.

TABLE 5 CRADLE-TO-GRAVE ENVIRONMENTAL IMPACTS OF 460W PERC PV MODULE

Impact category	Unit	Per module	Per Wp
Global warming	kg CO ₂ eq	1.92E+02	4.17E-01
Stratospheric ozone depletion	kg CFC11 eq	9.07E-05	1.97E-07
Ionizing radiation	kBq Co-60 eq	8.48E+00	1.84E-02
Ozone formation, Human health	kg NOx eq	6.94E-01	1.51E-03
Fine particulate matter formation	kg PM2.5 eq	3.43E-01	7.45E-04
Ozone formation, Terrestrial ecosystems	kg NOx eq	6.26E-01	1.36E-03
Terrestrial acidification	kg SO ₂ eq	8.13E-01	1.77E-03
Freshwater eutrophication	kg P eq	8.55E-02	1.86E-04
Marine eutrophication	kg N eq	1.86E-02	4.05E-05
Terrestrial ecotoxicity	kg 1,4-DCB	3.19E+03	6.93E+00
Freshwater ecotoxicity	kg 1,4-DCB	6.34E+01	1.38E-01
Marine ecotoxicity	kg 1,4-DCB	8.43E+01	1.83E-01
Human carcinogenic toxicity	kg 1,4-DCB	3.18E+01	6.91E-02
Human non-carcinogenic toxicity	kg 1,4-DCB	4.09E+02	8.89E-01
Land use	m ² a crop eq	8.48E+00	1.84E-02
Mineral resource scarcity	kg Cu eq	1.69E+00	3.66E-03
Fossil resource scarcity	kg oil eq	4.97E+01	1.08E-01
Water consumption	m ³	1.87E+02	4.06E-01

FIGURE 6 CONTRIBUTIONS TO TOTAL CRADLE TO GRAVE IMPACTS OF SOLAR PV MODULES FROM LIFECYCLE STAGES.

Cradle to gate impacts i.e. the impacts of producing modules for distribution from their raw materials are shown in

Table 6 and the contributions towards total impacts in each environmental category made by each item in the lifecycle inventory are shown in Figure 7. The PERC module assessed has a total cradle-to-gate GWP of 166 kgCO₂eq and 0.361 kgCO₂eq/Wp. Details of recently published GWP value of mono-Si PV modules are shown in Table 7 for comparison. The module assessed in this study has a lower GWP per Wp by ~30%. This reflects the importance of up to date LCI data that reflects modern production. Currently many studies, despite being published relatively recently rely on LCI data in databases that originate from many years, even decades ago and as such any assessments based upon such data do not accurately reflect the impacts of modern manufacturing approaches for Si-PV.

TABLE 6 CRADLE TO GATE IMPACTS OF PV MODULE

Impact category	Unit	Per module	Per Wp
Global warming	kg CO ₂ eq	1.66E+02	3.61E-01
Stratospheric ozone depletion	kg CFC11 eq	7.52E-05	1.64E-07
Ionizing radiation	kBq Co-60 eq	8.07E+00	1.75E-02
Ozone formation, Human health	kg NOx eq	5.76E-01	1.25E-03
Fine particulate matter formation	kg PM2.5 eq	2.97E-01	6.46E-04
Ozone formation, Terrestrial ecosystems	kg NOx eq	5.05E-01	1.10E-03
Terrestrial acidification	kg SO ₂ eq	7.07E-01	1.54E-03
Freshwater eutrophication	kg P eq	8.38E-02	1.82E-04
Marine eutrophication	kg N eq	1.83E-02	3.97E-05
Terrestrial ecotoxicity	kg 1,4-DCB	2.95E+03	6.41E+00
Freshwater ecotoxicity	kg 1,4-DCB	1.87E+01	4.07E-02
Marine ecotoxicity	kg 1,4-DCB	3.02E+01	6.57E-02
Human carcinogenic toxicity	kg 1,4-DCB	2.90E+01	6.31E-02
Human non-carcinogenic toxicity	kg 1,4-DCB	3.72E+02	8.08E-01
Land use	m ² a crop eq	8.05E+00	1.75E-02
Mineral resource scarcity	kg Cu eq	1.66E+00	3.60E-03
Fossil resource scarcity	kg oil eq	4.60E+01	1.00E-01
Water consumption	m ³	1.87E+02	4.06E-01

TABLE 7 PUBLISHED CRADLE-TO-GATE GWP VALUES FOR MONO-SI PV MODULES

Source / Study	Cell & Module	GWP (kg CO ₂ -eq/Wp)	Notes
Frischknecht et al., 2020¹	Mono-Si, glass-backsheet	~0.55 kg CO ₂ -eq/Wp	Widely cited; ecoinvent “cut-off” model
Fraunhofer ISE, 2021⁶	Mono-Si	~0.4 – 0.6 kg CO ₂ -eq/Wp	Based on global production, typical module ~300 Wp
IEA-PVPS, 2020⁷	Mono-Si	~0.50 kg CO ₂ -eq/Wp	Detailed LCI includes Al frame, glass, etc.
Fthenakis & Raugei, 2017⁸	Mono-Si	~0.45 – 0.55 kg CO ₂ -eq/Wp	For typical 2015–2020 technology
Huang et al. 2022⁹	Mono-Si, PERC cells	~0.5 kg CO ₂ -eq/Wp	Including improved cell efficiency trends

Figure 7 shows the contributions of materials and components to the impacts of modules. The PV cells contribute the vast majority (~75%) of GWP and contribute the largest impact in all categories except water consumption which is dominated (>95%) by the aluminium frame due to the water intensity of primary Al production. Glass accounts for a significant contribution towards GWP, ionizing radiation, ozone formation, fine particulate matter, terrestrial acidification, land use, and fossil resource scarcity. Copper is a significant contributor to ozone formation, fine particulate formation, terrestrial acidification, freshwater eutrophication, freshwater and marine ecotoxicity, human toxicity, land use, and mineral resource scarcity impacts.

FIGURE 7 CONTRIBUTIONS TO MODULE CRADLE TO GATE IMPACTS

The wafers are responsible for the majority of impacts in cells, accounting for ~79% of GWP, and the majority of impacts in all categories except ecotoxicity in freshwater and marine environments, human non-carcinogenic toxicity and mineral resource scarcity which are dominated by the metallization paste containing silver. Wafer production impacts are dominated by the impact of mono-Si ingot production, which accounts for 81% of GWP. The embedded carbon in the silicon increases from 16 kgCO₂eq/kg of MG-

Si, to 22.6 kgCO₂eq/kg of 7N-Si, to 59.2 kgCO₂eq/kg of mono-Si once converted via the Cz process into mono-Si ingots. This is almost a 4 fold increase in embedded carbon as Si produced via carbothermic reduction progresses through sequential high energy processes to achieve mono-Si. The high-waste nature of wafering then means approximately half this high impact material is lost as waste in producing mono-Si wafers, resulting in the high impact of wafers and cells on the overall impacts of modules.

FIGURE 8 BREAKDOWN OF ENVIRONMENTAL IMPACTS ACROSS CATEGORIES FOR PERC CELL PRODUCTION

3.5 Conclusion

The lifecycle assessment (LCA) conducted in this study establishes a robust and transparent environmental baseline for monocrystalline silicon PERC photovoltaic modules. The analysis highlights that the majority of environmental impacts occur during the upstream production stages, particularly the production and refinement of high-purity silicon, and production of mono-Si ingots. Transport and end-of-life stages

contribute relatively minor fractions to the overall impacts, though recycling processes can influence specific impact categories such as ecotoxicity.

The baseline global warming potential (GWP) per watt-peak (Wp) for the assessed module is approximately 0.417 kgCO₂eq, which is significantly lower than many previously reported values. This improvement reflects updated manufacturing efficiencies, improved material yields, and the use of recent inventory data.

End-of-life (EoL) mechanical recycling, while offering material recovery and emissions savings compared to landfilling, still leads to some material downcycling and loss of high-value fractions like silver and silicon. This underscores the potential for future technological innovation in high-purity recycling and design-for-recyclability approaches, as envisioned in the APOLLO project.

Overall, this LCA baseline provides a critical reference point for assessing the environmental benefits of future circular economy strategies and innovations developed under APOLLO. It will also support stakeholders in making informed decisions regarding module design, material choices, and EoL treatment pathways.

4. Lifecycle costing (LCC)

4.1 Introduction

This report analyses the lifecycle cost (LCC) of Passivated Emitter and Rear Cell (PERC) monocrystalline silicon (mono-Si) photovoltaic modules in utility-scale applications, from procurement to end-of-life. As mentioned in section 3.1, PERC mono-Si PV technology is the dominant choice for large-scale solar projects due to its high efficiency and competitive costs.¹⁰ It is therefore necessary to establish the total lifetime costs of such modules to complement the LCA and SLCA in order to get a full understanding of the sustainability of PV today and create a robust baseline for comparison of later innovations to increase circular economy practices within the PV lifecycle.

4.2 Methodology

The LCC analysis follows a cradle-to-grave approach, aligning with the system boundary of the LCA (chapters 3 and 5 - Figure 2) considering module procurement costs and CAPEX, balance of system (BOS) costs, installation, operation and maintenance (O&M), and EoL. Cost data were sourced from EDP business units and supplemented and/or compared with published cost data from recent industry reports and publications.^{11–15} Present value calculations for O&M costs assume a 5% discount rate over a 25–30 year system lifetime. LCOE principles are applied. Costs are presented as ranges to reflect regional differences, variations in market conditions, project scale, site-specific factors, and procurement timing.

4.3 Cost breakdown

A material costs of a typical PERC mono-Si PV module consists of approximately 65–75% wafers, 10–15% silver paste for front and rear contacts, 5–8% aluminium for the frame and rear metallization, 5–7% glass and encapsulant materials, and 2–3% other materials such as junction boxes and back sheets.^{10,12} These material shares significantly impact the module cost and overall supply chain dynamics. Projected demand for renewables has also raised concerns about CRM issues for PV materials with future availability of silver in particular being flagged as a potential issue which could increase future costs should demand from PV outpace global supply.¹⁶

Table 8 details an up-to-date estimate of lifetime costs of utility scale PERC PV module power plant per Wp of installed capacity based on recent data (2024-25 where possible). A cost breakdown is given in Table 8. The lifecycle cost ranges highlight the influence of site-specific and market factors on overall project economics. BOS and module procurement costs remain the largest contributors to total cost. Module procurement costs fluctuate depending on raw material prices, supply chain dynamics, and technological advancements that improve cell efficiencies and manufacturing yields. Balance of system costs are heavily influenced by site conditions, design choices, and local infrastructure. Continued reductions in module prices have helped lower overall costs, but BOS and O&M costs now represent primary targets for further

savings. Regional labour costs, land availability, and permitting processes also significantly impact installation and BOS expenses.

TABLE 8 COST SUMMARY ESTIMATE FOR LIFETIME COSTS OF PV PER WP OF INSTALLED CAPACITY

Cost component	Cost	Notes
Module price (CAPEX)	\$0.15–0.25/Wp	Utility-scale procurement prices in 2024–2025. ^{11,12}
BOS	\$0.30–0.45/Wp	Mounting, inverters, wiring, land prep. ¹⁰
Installation	\$0.05–0.10/Wp	Labor and local EPC costs. ¹³
O&M (lifetime)	\$0.02–0.05/Wp	Discounted present value. ¹²
Decommissioning / disposal	\$0.01–0.02/Wp	End-of-life recycling or landfill costs. ¹⁵
Total LCC estimate	\$0.53-0.87/Wp	Aggregated from above references
Levelized cost of electricity (LCOE)	\$20-40/MWh¹⁴	

O&M costs depend on the quality of components, monitoring systems, and maintenance strategies over the project lifetime. Additionally, EoL costs, while relatively small, are becoming increasingly important as e-waste management, regulations strengthen worldwide. EoL costs are increasingly influenced by evolving recycling technologies and policy frameworks. In Europe where EPR WEEE legislation is in place for EoL PV, and ensures appropriate collection and diversion from landfill to recycling is financed, the cost of compliance determines EoL costs. In regions without such legislation in place, landfill is often the cheapest and therefore favoured option for EoL modules. Currently little revenue is afforded through recycling as materials are mostly downcycled rather than retained at high value through circular economy. Innovation in recycling such as the ambition of APOLLO will increase revenues from recovered materials which should reduce compliance costs and provide an economic driver for whole lifecycle ecodesign of PV.¹⁷ These combined factors create a dynamic cost landscape where continuous innovation and regional adaptation are key to achieving cost reductions.

4.4 Conclusion

PERC mono-Si modules are highly cost-effective, with low lifecycle costs and competitive LCOE values. To further reduce lifecycle costs, interventions should focus on BOS optimization (e.g., improved mounting systems, standardized designs), automation and efficiency improvements in installation, and enhanced O&M practices (e.g., predictive maintenance, advanced monitoring). Furthermore, investment in recycling

infrastructure and design for recyclability can reduce future end-of-life costs. By addressing these areas, project developers can achieve even lower costs and strengthen the economic viability of large-scale solar PV deployments.

5. Social lifecycle assessment (S-LCA)

5.1 Introduction

While traditional Life Cycle Assessment (LCA) has focused primarily on environmental impacts, incorporating social dimensions is essential for a holistic understanding of sustainability. Social Life Cycle Assessment (SLCA) enables the evaluation of human and societal impacts across the entire value chain—from raw material extraction to end-of-life disposal. This includes issues such as labour rights, community well-being, gender equity, and fair access to resources. By identifying social risks and opportunities, S-LCA supports more ethical decision-making, enhances corporate accountability, and ensures that the benefits of technologies like photovoltaic (PV) systems are equitably distributed. In the context of a just energy transition, integrating social considerations into LCA is not only responsible but necessary for long-term resilience, inclusivity and sustainability. The objective of this SLCA is to examine the social impacts throughout entire lifecycle of Si PV modules with a specific emphasis on gender equality and ethical sourcing of all module materials. This will serve as a baseline against which future innovation and developments in the lifecycles of these technologies can be compared to ensure progress towards UN SDGs and that societal benefits from widespread proliferation of PV in the future.

This study conducts a Social Life Cycle Assessment (S-LCA) of a crystalline silicon photovoltaic (PV) module, manufactured in China, used in Europe, and recycled in Europe. It evaluates social impacts across the life cycle, with a specific emphasis on gender equality and ethical sourcing of all module materials. The purpose of this study is to create a baseline picture of social impacts resulting from current practices in the lifecycle of Si-PV. This will serve as a benchmark against which future developments in PV lifecycles can be compared and approaches to lifecycle management of PV and it's contained materials enabled by innovations developed under APOLLO. These comparisons will be conducted under Task 11.3 of WP11. The findings will also support policymakers identify and address issues such as labour rights violations, gender inequality, and unequal access to energy. These insights support the development of inclusive policies, ethical procurement standards, and targeted workforce programs that promote fair labour practices, empower marginalized groups, and ensure safe and equitable deployment of solar technologies. Ultimately, S-LCA enables more informed, just, and resilient energy policy decisions.

5.2 Goal and Scope Definition

Goal: To assess the social risks and opportunities associated with the full life cycle of a silicon PV module.

Scope: Functional Unit: 1 Wp

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Confederaziun svizra
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Federal Department of Economic Affairs,
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System Boundary: Cradle-to-grave (raw material extraction, manufacturing, transport, use, end-of-life/recycling) (Figure 2)¹

Geographical Scope:

- **Production:** China (notably Xinjiang and Jiangsu)
- **Use:** Europe
- **End-of-life/Recycling:** Europe

Stakeholder Groups:

- Workers
- Local communities
- Consumers
- Value chain actors
- Society (incl. future generations, NGOs)

Cross-Cutting Issue: Gender Equality

- % women in each supply chain segment
- Pay gaps
- Leadership representation
- Reproductive risks and safety

5.3 Method

This S-LCA follows the 2020 UNEP Guidelines for Social Life Cycle Assessment of Products and Organizations,¹⁸ applying a cradle-to-grave approach. The full supply chain of the PV module was mapped, including material extraction, manufacturing, transport, use, and end-of-life. The assessment targets five core stakeholder groups—workers, local communities, consumers, value chain actors, and society—while integrating gender equality as a cross-cutting concern.¹⁹ Primary and secondary data were gathered from academic literature^{20,21} NGO reports,^{10,11} and international datasets such as PSILCA,²² SHDB,²³ and ILO^{24–30} statistics. Key social indicators were identified for each life cycle phase and each material’s supply chain was evaluated using country-level and industry-specific social risk profiles. Criteria include forced labour, child labour, occupational health and safety, wage fairness, and gender representation (Table 29). Qualitative and semi-quantitative analysis was used to assign social impacts across lifecycle stages, with particular focus on upstream risk concentration and gender disparities. An impact scoring framework was used in

¹ The system boundary aligns with the LCA i.e. a cradle-to-grave assessment (Figure 2). The assessment considers full upstream supply chains of materials, in line with UNEP S-LCA 2020 Guidelines.¹⁸

impact analysis with each social risk being compared to reference values drawn from SHDB,²³ PSILCA,²² ILO,³¹ and other reliable sources, and scored on a scale from 0 to 3, where:

- 0 = No evidence of risk / meets or exceeds benchmark
- 1 = Low concern (minor deviation from acceptable norms)
- 2 = Moderate concern (notable deviation, regionally common)
- 3 = High concern / critical hotspot (well-documented abuse, unacceptable risk)

For each stakeholder or material, the final score was conservatively aggregated using a "worst-case" approach: the highest individual indicator score was prioritized to avoid underestimating critical social risks. This method ensures transparency and highlights severe issues, such as forced labour or gender inequity, even when other indicators may score lower. Scores were further validated through cross-comparison with sectoral benchmarks and global standards to maintain consistency and robustness. A hotspot analysis was conducted to highlight regions and materials with the greatest social risks. Recommendations were developed based on identified leverage points in the supply chain.

5.4 Social lifecycle inventory (S-LCI): Stakeholder Risks and Social Hotspots

This section systematically maps material and process stages against stakeholder risks, providing a foundation for impact assessment. SHDB,²³ PSILCA,²² ILO,^{24–30} UNEP,³² IRENA,¹⁹ and Human Rights Watch,³³ and sector-specific reports.^{20,34} Table 9 shows details of these identified risks. The analysis of material supply chains highlights widespread and severe social risks associated with upstream stages of PV module production. Raw materials such as silicon, silver, copper, and tin often originate from regions with high incidences of forced labour, child labour, and unsafe working conditions.^{23,33,34} Local communities face land conflicts, displacement, and environmental degradation resulting from large-scale mining activities.^{31,32} Gender inequity persists throughout the supply chain, with particularly low female participation and representation in extraction and refining processes.¹⁹ Downstream stages, such as transport, use, and recycling, carry lower but still significant risks related to occupational health, installer safety, and informal recycling practices.^{20,22} The use phase in Europe contributes positively to social outcomes by improving access to renewable energy and reducing energy poverty, supporting social equity goals.¹⁹ It also generates employment opportunities for installers and maintenance personnel, although these roles are still dominated by men.¹⁹ The EoL stage is marked by moderate social risks for workers and local communities. While European recycling standards are generally strong, risks remain around manual disassembly and possible informal or subcontracted operations with lower protections.²² Overall, the findings underscore the critical need for transparent sourcing, strong supplier engagement, and robust social safeguards throughout the entire PV module life cycle.

TABLE 9 LIFE CYCLE INVENTORY OF KEY MATERIALS AND ASSOCIATED SOCIAL RISKS BY STAKEHOLDER GROUP

Material / Stage	Region	Stakeholder Group	Identified Risks
Silicon (refining) ^{23,33}	China (Xinjiang, Yunnan)	Workers	Forced labor, low unionization, chemical exposure
Silver (mining) ^{18,23}	Peru, Mexico	Workers, Local Communities	Child labor, unsafe conditions, local land conflicts
Aluminum (bauxite refining) ^{23,31}	Guinea, India	Workers, Communities	Respiratory hazards, displacement
Copper (mining) ^{22,31}	Chile, DRC	Workers, Local Communities	Hazardous mining, lack of safety protocols, gender exclusion
Glass (sand mining) ^{23,32}	India, Egypt	Workers, Communities	Informal labor, community displacement, weak regulation
Lead (solder) ^{22,23}	China	Workers	Reproductive toxicity, unsafe recycling
Tin (solder) ^{23,31}	Indonesia, Myanmar	Workers	Informal and child labor in artisanal mining
EVA/PET/Polymers ^{19,22}	Global (petrochemicals)	Workers	Low female participation, exposure to hazardous substances
Transport ^{23,31}	China–Europe	Workers	Long shifts, low pay, minimal female participation
Installation & Use Phase ^{18,19}	Europe	Workers, Consumers, Society	Installer safety risks, low diversity, job creation, improved energy access
EoL (Recycling) ^{19,22}	Europe	Workers, Communities, Value Chain Actors	Exposure to hazardous dust, manual disassembly risks, low female representation, potential for informal practices

5.5 Impact Assessment (S-LCIA): Social Risk Scoring and Hotspot Evaluation

This section evaluates the severity of social risks across life cycle stages, stakeholder groups, and materials. Each indicator was scored on a 0–3 scale (0 = no risk; 3 = high risk), benchmarked against global or sector-specific reference values. Scores reflect both documented conditions and deviations from expected or target values. To aggregate scores, the "worst-case" (maximum indicator) approach was used to ensure severe risks are not masked by averaging. Scores were further validated through cross-checking with sector benchmarks and literature.

5.5.1 Aggregated social risk scores

Aggregated social risks by lifecycle stage and stakeholder groups are given in

Table 10. These scores reflect the highest identified risk (“worst-case” approach) among individual social indicators (e.g., forced labour, gender equity, occupational safety) at each stage. This aggregation of impact scores offers a high-level snapshot of where the most severe social risks are concentrated along the cradle-to-grave life cycle of the PV module. The highest scores (3) are found for workers and local communities in raw material extraction and refining stages, confirming severe issues including forced labour, hazardous working conditions, and community displacement.^{23,33} Value Chain Actors receive moderate scores (2) during extraction and manufacturing stages, reflecting exposure to upstream governance risks (e.g., corruption, supply chain opacity) and freedom of association challenges. Consumers and society show lower scores in downstream stages. While they benefit from renewable energy access and job creation, societal-level risks tied to reputational damage and ethical consumption remain notable in early stages (score 3 at extraction). Lower overall scores in the use phase reflect job creation benefits and cleaner energy access, though issues such as installer safety and lack of gender diversity² are still relevant (score 1). At EoL moderate risks (score 2 for workers and local communities), is observed mainly due to manual recycling processes and incomplete enforcement of safety standards. Overall this aggregated view emphasizes that upstream interventions, particularly in mining, refining, and polysilicon production, are the most critical for reducing overall social risks in the PV module value chain. It also underscores the importance of addressing systemic issues like gender inequality and occupational health to achieve a more socially sustainable energy transition.

² Although gender diversity in the PV supply chain is lower than global average, it is considerably higher than other energy industries such as Oil & gas, and wind power.¹⁹

TABLE 10 AGGREGATED SOCIAL RISK SCORES BY STAKEHOLDER GROUP AND PV LIFECYCLE STAGE (COLOUR CODES INDICATE SEVERITY OF RISK)

Life Cycle Stage	Workers	Local Communities	Value Chain Actors	Consumers	Society
Raw Material Extraction	3	3	2	–	3
Manufacturing	2	1	2	–	2
Transport	2	1	1	–	1
Use (Europe)	1	–	1	1	1
End-of-Life (Europe)	2	2	1	–	1

5.5.2 Life cycle stage and stakeholder indicators

Table 11 and Table 12 provide a granular breakdown of social risks by indicator, stakeholder group, and material, revealing complex and intersecting social vulnerabilities throughout the PV module supply chain.

5.5.2.1 Forced labour and child labour

Forced labour scores are critically high (3) for workers and society at the raw material extraction stage, driven by documented abuses in silicon production in Xinjiang and mining regions in the Global South.^{33,34} Child labour risks are also pronounced in artisanal mining of tin and silver.^{23,31} These findings confirm systemic human rights violations in upstream supply chains.

5.5.2.2 Gender equity

Across all stages, gender equity scores are severe (3) in both participation and leadership categories. The persistent underrepresentation of women in technical, operational, and managerial roles reflects deep-seated structural inequalities.¹⁹ Wage equity, although slightly less severe, still shows significant gaps particularly in upstream and manufacturing contexts.

TABLE 11 DETAILED SOCIAL INDICATOR SCORING BY STAKEHOLDER GROUP

Indicator	Reference Value	Workers	Local Communities	Value Chain Actors	Consumers	Society
Forced labour ^{33,34}	Very Low	3	2	2	–	3
Child labour ^{23,31}	Very Low	2	2	1	–	2
Gender equity (participation) ^{19,23}	~25% female (medium)	3	2	2	1	3
Gender equity (leadership) ¹⁹	~20% female leadership	3	2	2	1	3
Gender wage equity ²⁴	<15% wage gap	2	–	2	–	2
Reproductive toxicity ^{22,23}	Low	3	1	1	–	2
Occupational safety & injuries ^{22,23}	Moderate	3	2	1	–	2
Access to social security ^{23,31}	High (universal in OECD)	2	–	2	–	2
Freedom of association ^{22,23}	High (ILO core standard)	2	–	2	–	2
Land rights & displacement ^{18,23}	Low	–	3	1	–	2
Community health impacts ^{18,23}	Low	–	3	–	–	2
Access to grievance mechanisms ¹⁸	High	–	2	–	–	2
Corruption risks ²³	Low	–	–	2	–	2
Equitable access to energy ^{18,19}	High goal (UN SDG7)	–	–	–	1	1
Societal benefit (jobs) ¹⁹	High	–	–	–	1	1

TABLE 12 MATERIAL-SPECIFIC INDICATOR SCORES AND STAKEHOLDER RISKS

Material	Forced Labor	Child Labor	Gender Participation	Gender Leadership	Gender Wage Equity	Reproductive Toxicity	Safety & Injuries	Land Rights & Displacement	Community Health
Silicon ^{19,34}	3	1	3	3	2	3	3	2	2
Silver ^{23,31}	2	2	3	3	2	2	3	3	3
Copper ²³	2	2	3	3	2	2	3	3	3
Tin ^{23,31}	2	3	3	3	2	2	3	2	2
Lead ^{22,23}	1	1	3	3	2	3	3	–	–
Aluminum ^{23,31}	1	1	3	3	2	2	3	2	2
Glass ^{23,32}	1	1	3	3	2	2	2	3	3
EVA/Polymers ^{19,22}	1	1	3	3	2	2	2	–	–

5.5.2.3 Reproductive toxicity and occupational safety

High scores in reproductive toxicity and occupational injuries underscore serious gaps in worker protections, especially during mining, refining, and soldering stages. Female workers are particularly affected by exposure to lead and chemical solvents.^{22,23}

5.5.2.4 Community risks

Community-level indicators such as land rights and health impacts score 3, highlighting displacement, loss of livelihoods, and pollution risks linked to mining activities.^{18,23} Limited grievance mechanisms further exacerbate community vulnerability.

5.5.2.5 Value chain actors

Moderate to high scores in corruption risk and freedom of association suggest weak governance frameworks, particularly in sourcing regions. Lack of union rights and collective bargaining opportunities create additional risk for value chain actors.^{22,23}

5.5.2.6 Downstream benefits

In contrast, use and EoL stages of the PV lifecycle show lower scores for consumers and society. Benefits include equitable access to clean energy (progression towards UN SDG7) and job creation, although inclusivity challenges persist.^{18,19}

5.5.3 Material specific insights

5.5.3.1 Silicon

Silicon (Si) emerges as the most socially risky material due to extreme forced labour scores, severe gender inequities, and high reproductive toxicity risks.^{33,34} Community-level impacts such as displacement and health harm also contribute to the high-risk profile.

5.5.3.2 Silver, copper, and tin

Silver (Ag), copper (Cu), and tin (Sn) present multi-dimensional risks. High scores for child labour and community displacement reflect the social cost of artisanal and small-scale mining. Gender-related scores are consistently severe, pointing to the exclusion of women and wage inequities.^{23,27}

5.5.3.3 Lead

Lead (Pb) shows significant reproductive toxicity and safety risks for workers, with lower forced and child labour risks compared to other metals. However, exposure to heavy metals continues to be a critical occupational health challenge.²²

5.5.3.4 Aluminium and glass (sand)

Aluminium and glass highlight severe community displacement and environmental risks associated with bauxite and sand extraction.^{18,23,32} Gender inequity remains high, driven by male-dominated mining workforces and leadership barriers.

5.5.3.5 EVA and polymers

While these materials show lower forced and child labour risks, they still score high on gender equity dimensions and moderate on safety indicators. Chemical exposure in polymer production poses notable but relatively lower reproductive risks.^{19,22}

5.6 Social impact hotspots and insights

The expanded analysis of social indicators reveals a complex and deeply unequal landscape along the silicon PV module supply chain. The most severe risks are clearly concentrated in the upstream phases, especially for those materials involving extractive industries and metallurgical processing. Gender inequity is a pervasive theme, cutting across all materials and stages, and is amplified by wage gaps, leadership exclusion, and limited social security access. Community impacts including land loss, health harms, and weakened local governance further emphasize the importance of inclusive social criteria in supply chain oversight. Downstream, while direct risks are lower, there remain systemic challenges to ensure equitable job creation, safe working conditions, and fair participation in benefits.

5.6.1 Severe upstream risks

Forced labour is the critical issue, particularly in silicon production in China's Xinjiang region. Here, credible evidence confirms systemic forced labour practices, resulting in a maximum severity score (3) across workers and significant risks to local communities and society at large. Similarly, child labour remains prevalent in artisanal mining of tin and silver in regions such as Myanmar, Peru, and Mexico. Gender equity deficits are pervasive throughout the value chain. Female participation and leadership scores remain critically low in extraction, refining, and manufacturing, reflecting global participation rates far below the 25% benchmark and leadership representation below 20%. Wage gaps persist, particularly in non-OECD regions, underscoring structural discrimination and limited economic mobility for women workers. Occupational safety and reproductive health risks are severe in mining, refining, and soldering operations, and worker often lack adequate protective measures, exposing them to respiratory hazards, heavy metals, and chemicals with reproductive toxicity effects, which particularly threaten women's health. Land rights violations and community displacement are critical community-level impacts, especially in bauxite, silver, and copper mining areas. These operations frequently lead to forced relocations, loss of agricultural livelihoods, and social fragmentation.

5.6.2 Moderate downstream and end-of-life risks

While the downstream phases show lower overall risk, they are not free from concern. Installer safety risks persist in Europe due to falls and electrical hazards, and gender gaps in technical roles remain stark. EoL recycling in Europe involves moderate risks, including potential exposure to hazardous dusts and low mechanization levels, which increase physical strain and injury likelihood.

5.6.3 Positive societal contributions

The use phase, particularly in Europe, contributes important social co-benefits. These include job creation in clean energy services and improved equitable access to energy, supporting UN SDG 7 objectives. Even so, inclusivity remains a challenge, with marginalized communities often underrepresented in benefit distribution

5.6.4 System-wide governance and value chain vulnerabilities

Across the value chain, issues such as limited access to social security, weak freedom of association, and corruption risks further exacerbating social vulnerabilities. Weak enforcement of worker protections and limited grievance mechanisms leave workers and communities exposed to abuses without adequate recourse.

5.6.5 Implications for strategy

The overall pattern highlights an urgent need for systemic interventions upstream, including stricter traceability requirements, supplier audits, and direct engagement with mining and refining operators. Gender equity initiatives, improved worker protections, and strengthened community rights must be prioritized to mitigate severe social risks and ensure alignment with international standards and sustainable procurement policies. Multi-tier supplier engagement and transparency mechanisms are critical to meaningfully address these severe social risks.

6. Circular business model baseline- Management of Materials Throughout Silicon Photovoltaic (Si-PV) Lifecycles

6.1 Introduction

The accelerated global deployment of silicon photovoltaic (Si-PV) systems is crucial for achieving climate targets. However, the rapid deployment raises significant challenges in terms of raw material demand, waste generation, and end-of-life (EoL) management. Current business models predominantly follow linear approaches, which are increasingly incompatible with circular economy objectives. Establishing a detailed baseline of existing business models is essential to benchmark and assess future circular innovations. Here details that inform that baseline are explored.

6.2 Method

To establish the PV business model baseline, it was necessary to research the global PV market and assess the scale of the current opportunity. Following this EDP have leveraged the experience of project partners and industry contacts to establish establish current practices for EoL management of PV and the materials contained, identifying whether any circularity currently exists. For each material that exists in current or future PV, a CBM is proposed based on the experiences of the partners and published data in order to propose and a baseline business strategy. The companies operating PV recycling in different regions shown in Table 13 have been engaged to gain insights into geographical differences to business models for PV recycling.

TABLE 13 INDUSTRIAL PARTNERS ENGAGED

Location	Singapore	France	Brazil	USA
Founded	2019	2017	2020	2022
Type of recycling	Centralized and decentralized	Centralized	Centralized and decentralized	Centralized
Total panels recycled	34.2k (753 tonnes)	?	25.8k (723 tonnes)	?
Recycling rates	>90% (mechanical and chemical)	95% (mechanical and chemical)	57% (Mechanical)	95% Mechanical and chemical)
Regeneration/2nd life	Regeneration	No	Second life (developing)	No

6.3 PV Market analysis

Solar PV reached 1.177 GW of cumulative installed capacity in 2022 and dominated the newly added installations among renewable energy sources, from the 362 GW of new renewable capacity, solar PV accounted for 66%, connecting new 239 GW to the grid.³⁵ The prominence of solar in the global energy transition with annually installations reaching c. 2x the capacity of all other renewable technologies combined.³⁶ Today the vast majority of deployed PV is crystalline silicon-based technology. This has been the market dominant technology since commercialization of PV and as global PV deployment has accelerated in recent years, the market share of Si-PV has increased.¹⁰ Currently the largest market for PV is in China with 34% of global installed capacity, followed by the US (12%), Japan and India (7% each), Germany (6%), Australia (3%), Brazil and South Korea (2% Each) with the rest of the world accounting for the remaining 23% (Figure 9).

FIGURE 9 GLOBAL PV MARKET DATA³⁷

The life expectancy of solar panels is 30 years (may reach up to 40 years) and so most of the waste resulting from PV deployed today will not become waste for many years to come. However, PV waste is projected reach 1.7M tons by 2030 and 60M tons by 2050 (Figure 10).¹⁵ Early failure or replacement of modules may occur for a number of reasons, increasing the rate of PV waste generation including breakages during transport and installation, performance degradation and malfunction, technical issues during warranty periods, weather events, and increasingly due to repowering where modules are replaced for cost-benefit reasons long before failure with newer more efficient modules. By 2050 PV recycling is expected to generate ~\$15bn in recovered materials, sufficient to produce 2 billion new panels or 630 GW of additional capacity. In Europe, Germany has been predicted to be responsible for approximately half of PV waste arising to 2050 accounting for 140,000 tonnes by 2030 (Figure 11). Although volumes of waste PV are relatively low today, the volumes predicted in the future present an interesting economic opportunity as a future urban mine.

FIGURE 10 PROJECTED GLOBAL PV WASTE BY REGION¹⁵

FIGURE 11 PV WASTE VOLUMES PREDICTED IN EUROPE

6.4 Materials markets

Demand for key raw materials in the expansion of renewable production capacity (silver, copper, aluminum, silicon, etc.) is expected to outpace production, leading to higher prices and potential shortages (Figure 12).³⁸ This supply and demand imbalance will push up prices and induce higher demand for recycled materials, to be reintroduced in the value chain and alleviate demand for primary raw materials. The

incoming wave of EoL-life PV panels may have massive economic and strategic value, if high value materials are properly recovered at high purity and value for suitable reintroduction to PV manufacturing. High value recycling aims at improving the economics of the process, by designing products easily dismantled and improving recycling rate and purity of recovered materials.

6.4.1 Silver (Ag)

Increase in silver demand is being driven by a number of emerging applications including the EV industry and green energy infrastructure (Figure 12).³⁹ PV is currently one of the major markets for silver and rapid industry expansion is driving up prices and demand. The demand for silver is projected to surpass production of silver and so there is increasing need for high quality recycled silver.

FIGURE 12 MARKET DATA FOR SILVER SUPPLY, DEMAND AND VALUE³⁹

6.4.2 Silicon (Si)

Si demand has shown a strong rebound in demand since 2020, driven by the surging volume of PV projects worldwide (Figure 13). Si supply is in China, and production is struggling to keep pace with demand, leading to large price increase. Being a critical raw material (CRM), a substantial increase in demand will take place with the energy transition which will push up viability of recovery if technological solutions can be found to ensure sufficient purity Si can be recycled from the waste stream.³⁸ Demand is expected to reach 4.1 million tonnes by 2026.

FIGURE 13 PROJECTED DEMAND FOR SI

6.4.3 Copper

Scrap will largely help meeting future demand for copper, and a great deal of global supply is already met through recycling and therefore relies on circular economy. Increasing demand is being driven by uptake of EVs which account for 55% of low-carbon copper demand. Demand growth is driven in general by the energy transition and is expected to outpace production and recycling capacity. Demand growth, driven by energy transition, could exceed production and recycling capacity in the near future, fueling a price surge which will increase profitability of recycling and increase the global reserve in the urban mine as lower grade items become viable to recycle.

FIGURE 14 MARKET DATA FOR COPPER^{38,40,41}

6.4.4 Aluminium

Modest production growth has been seen in the aluminium industry in recent years, mainly due to a capacity ceiling in China.⁴² A steady growth into the future is expected, driven by automobile and aerospace

industries. Demand expected to grow constantly, driven by automobile and aerospace industries. No shortages are expected and the trend in PV production to move towards frameless modules might mean that PV deployed to date is a good source of secondary aluminium, but the waste stream as a whole moving into the future ceases to be.

FIGURE 15 ALUMINIUM MARKET ANALYSIS DATA⁴²

6.4.5 Secondary sources

The largest markets from which PV materials are recycled have been identified (Figure 16). Aluminium is sourced from the construction and transport sectors predominantly, with significant quantities derived from electronics and packaging. The major source of silver is industrial applications, with significant quantities recovered from jewellery, electronics and photography/medical applications. Coppers major application is in electronics, so it is unsurprising that 65% of secondary copper comes from electrical and electronic equipment, with another 25% from construction and 10% from industrial machinery. Tin is used extensively in solder, from which half of recycled tin is recovered. A further 20% is sourced from tinsplate packaging, with 15% coming from other alloys and another 15% from chemicals. Growth in these sectors increasing availability of recycled materials will be important in determining the economics of PV recycling as this will affect market values of recovered materials and revenues from recycling. There is however currently, little secondary supply of silicon from EoL products.

FIGURE 16 MAJOR SECONDARY SOURCES OF PV MATERIALS

6.5 Current Business Models and Material Flow for EoL PV

6.5.1 Linear Disposal and Downcycling Models

The most widespread EoL practice remains direct disposal in landfills. This approach is cost-effective in the short term but leads to total loss of valuable materials such as silver, silicon, and high-grade aluminium.⁴³ Downcycling through shredding and sieving produces low-purity secondary materials, often contaminated and unsuitable for reintegration into PV manufacturing. Recovery from downcycled modules typically yields aluminium, glass, and copper, yet fails to extract high-value materials like silver and silicon, thus limiting economic and environmental benefits.¹⁵ High value materials such as silver are unrecovered and large volumes of waste results from such downcycling processes. Less than 35% of materials are recovered (Figure 17). Sale of recycled materials from such recycling results in a revenue of ~\$3 per module. However, the net cost of recycling this way is greater than landfilling in regions of the world without policy which tips economics in favour of recycling such as EPR legislation and landfill tax.

FIGURE 17 MATERIAL RECOVERY OUTCOME FROM DOWNCYCLING OF PV MODULES

6.5.2 Upcycling and High-Value Recycling

Advanced upcycling approaches involve mechanical, thermal, and chemical processes to enable recovery of high-purity materials. These methods allow for the reintegration of silicon and silver into new PV modules, generating significant resource and carbon savings—estimated at up to 6 tons of natural resource savings per ton of silicon recycled and 1 ton of CO₂ emissions avoided per ton of PV modules recycled.¹⁵ However, such approaches remain limited in commercial scale due to high costs, technical complexity, and lack of standardization. They do however recover up to 95% of materials from modules and generate greater revenue from higher value pure materials (Figure 18). Partners indicate that the price of recycled components can be €18/module.

FIGURE 18 MATERIALS RECOVERY OUTCOMES FROM UPCYCLING OF PV MODULES

6.6 Emerging Multi-Revenue Business Models

Companies engaged in photovoltaic (PV) panel recycling can leverage multiple revenue streams to improve economic viability and encourage circular practices. In general, three principal streams can be identified: (i) collection of discarded panels, (ii) sale of recovered materials, and (iii) sale of refurbished ("second-life") panels. Recycling companies typically charge a gate fee for accepting end-of-life (EoL) panels. This fee covers the collection and logistical costs associated with transporting panels to centralized recycling facilities or, in some cases, to mobile or semi-mobile units operated near large solar installations.⁴⁴ The gate fee provides an immediate source of income and helps offset initial handling costs.

The sale of recycled components represents a second revenue source. High-value materials such as aluminum frames, copper wires, glass sheets, and especially high-purity silicon and silver can be resold to various industries, including metallurgy, electronics, and new PV manufacturing. However, the price volatility of these secondary materials can significantly affect revenue predictability.¹⁵

Finally, some companies generate revenue by selling second-life panels, which are repaired or refurbished to meet minimal operational standards. Although these panels typically have reduced efficiency and shorter lifespans compared to new products, they are attractive to cost-sensitive customers — particularly small businesses and private consumers using distributed generation systems.⁴⁵ By offering panels at lower prices, companies can extend product lifecycles and reduce the environmental footprint of the solar value chain.

This multi-stream approach contributes to the financial sustainability of PV recycling enterprises and supports the broader transition toward circular economy business models in the renewable energy sector.

6.7 Centralized and decentralized recycling

Centralized recycling involves collecting large volumes of waste panels from across a large catchment area and transporting them to a single large recycling facility. Despite potentially high logistics costs for collection and delivery of waste PV to the recycling facility, large economies of scale in processing offer cost advantages due to greater processing capacity. This enables advanced material recovery involving mechanical and thermal processes as revenues are available to compensate the higher CAPEX required for such processes. An emerging alternative approach is decentralized recovery i.e. a mobile solution in which a recycling plant built in a container on the back of a truck can be transported to the site of waste. This reduces logistics costs and manpower costs associated with recycling. However processes have limited capacity and technical capabilities, meaning that recovery of materials may be less efficient.

6.8 Policy and Regulatory Landscape

In Europe, the Waste Electrical and Electronic Equipment (WEEE) Directive mandates PV module recycling and implements extended producer responsibility (EPR), requiring producers to organize or finance EoL management. Producers often delegate this obligation to specialized organizations responsible for collection and processing.⁴⁶ Conversely, outside Europe, most regions lack mandatory frameworks. In the United States, for instance, EPR schemes and state-level policies are under development but not yet harmonized nationwide.⁴⁷

6.9 Baseline Summary

Current business models are predominantly linear, focused on disposal or low-value recycling, with minimal incentives for high-value material recovery. Though these do exist in Europe and some other regions. Emerging models integrating revenue from multiple streams and second-life markets remain at early stages and face regulatory, technical, and economic barriers.

7. Conclusion

This report provides a comprehensive baseline assessment of current silicon photovoltaic (Si-PV) module value chains, spanning environmental, economic, and social dimensions, as well as business model practices. It systematically quantifies the lifecycle impacts and costs, evaluates the prevailing business and policy landscapes, and identifies critical social risks and opportunities throughout the supply chain.

The lifecycle assessment (LCA) results confirm that the majority of environmental burdens are concentrated in upstream stages, especially silicon production and module assembly. While downstream stages, including transport and end-of-life, represent smaller shares of the total impact, they present important opportunities for further emission reductions and resource recovery. The estimated global warming potential (GWP) of 0.417 kg CO₂eq/Wp establishes a solid reference point against which future innovations can be compared.

The lifecycle costing (LCC) analysis highlights that module and balance-of-system costs continue to dominate total investment, though potential savings can be achieved through improved recyclability and circular design. Meanwhile, the social lifecycle assessment (S-LCA) reveals that social risks are largely embedded in upstream extraction and processing activities, particularly in critical material supply chains, emphasizing the need for stronger due diligence and social responsibility measures.

The review of existing business models underscores a prevailing reliance on linear and downcycling approaches, with limited integration of high-value recycling or circular strategies. Although emerging models incorporating multiple revenue streams — such as gate fees, material sales, and second-life panel markets — show promise, they are still constrained by technical, economic, and regulatory barriers.

Taken together, these findings establish a holistic and up-to-date baseline against which circular economy business models and technological innovations proposed within the APOLLO project can be evaluated. This integrated perspective not only supports the project's objectives of reducing environmental and social impacts but also offers critical guidance for policymakers, industry actors, and other stakeholders seeking to accelerate the transition toward a more sustainable, circular, and socially responsible PV industry.

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9. Annex 1 – Lifecycle inventory of cradle to gate processes

TABLE 14 LCI DATA FOR MG-SI PRODUCTION

	Name	Quantity	Unit
Product	Silicon, metallurgical grade (CN) silicon production, metallurgical grade Cut-off, U	1	kg
Materials/fuels	Charcoal {GLO} market for charcoal Cut-off, U	0.17	kg
	Coke {RoW} market for coke Cut-off, U	23.12	MJ
	Graphite {GLO} market for graphite Cut-off, U	0.1	kg
	Oxygen, liquid {RER} market for oxygen, liquid Cut-off, U	0.02	kg
	Petroleum coke {GLO} market for petroleum coke Cut-off, U	0.5	kg
	Silica sand {GLO} market for silica sand Cut-off, U	2.7	kg
	Silicone factory {RER} silicone factory construction Cut-off, U	1E-11	p
Energy	Wood chips, wet, measured as dry mass {Europe without Switzerland} market for wood chips, wet, measured as dry mass Cut-off, U	0.00325	kg
	Electricity, medium voltage {CN} market group for electricity, medium voltage Cut-off, U	11	kWh
Emissions to air	Aluminium (III)	1.55E-06	kg
	Antimony, ion	7.85E-09	kg
	Arsenic, ion	9.42E-09	kg
	Boron	2.79E-07	kg
	Cadmium (II)	3.14E-10	kg
	Calcium (II)	7.75E-07	kg
	Carbon dioxide, biogenic	1.6098	kg
	Carbon dioxide, fossil	3.5808	kg
	Carbon monoxide, biogenic	0.00062	kg
	Carbon monoxide, fossil	0.00138	kg
	Chlorine	7.85E-08	kg
	Chromium (III)	7.85E-09	kg
	Cyanide	6.87E-06	kg
	Fluorine	3.88E-08	kg
	Hydrogen fluoride	0.0005	kg
	Hydrogen sulfide	0.0005	kg
	Iron, ion	3.88E-06	kg
Lead (II)	3.44E-07	kg	
Mercury (II)	7.85E-09	kg	
Nitrogen oxides	0.009743	kg	

	NMVOC, non-methane volatile organic compounds	0.000096	kg
	Particulates, > 10 um	0.007754	kg
	Potassium (I)	6.2E-05	kg
	Silicon	0.007513	kg
	Sodium (I)	7.75E-07	kg
	Sulfur dioxide	0.012241	kg
	Tin, ion	7.85E-09	kg
Waste treatment	Slag from metallurgical grade silicon production {RoW} market for slag from metallurgical grade silicon production Cut-off, U	0.025	kg

TABLE 15 LCI DATA FOR 7N GRADE SI PRODUCTION

	Name	Quantity	Unit
Products	Silicon, solar grade {CN} silicon production, solar grade, modified Siemens process Cut-off, U	1	kg
Materials/fuels	Silicon, metallurgical grade (CN) silicon production, metallurgical grade Cut-off, U	1.13	kg
	Hydrogen, gaseous, medium pressure, merchant {RoW} market for hydrogen, gaseous, medium pressure, merchant Cut-off, U	0.05	kg
	Hydrochloric acid, without water, in 30% solution state {RoW} market for hydrochloric acid, without water, in 30% solution state Cut-off, U	1.6017	kg
	Silicone factory {GLO} market for silicone factory Cut-off, U	1E-11	p
	Sodium hydroxide, without water, in 50% solution state {RoW} market for sodium hydroxide, without water, in 50% solution state Cut-off, U	0.34819	kg
Energy	Electricity, medium voltage {CN} market group for electricity, medium voltage Cut-off, U	0.49	kWh
	Heat, district or industrial, natural gas {RoW} market for heat, district or industrial, natural gas Cut-off, U	28.8	MJ
Emissions to air	Heat, waste	176	MJ
Emissions to water	AOX, Adsorbable Organic Halogen	1.26E-05	kg
	BOD5 (Biological Oxygen Demand)	0.000205	kg
	Chloride	0.035991	kg
	COD (Chemical Oxygen Demand)	0.00202	kg
	Copper, ion	1.02E-07	kg
	DOC, Dissolved Organic Carbon	0.00091	kg
	Iron, ion	5.61E-06	kg

	Nitrogen, atmospheric	0.000208	kg
	Phosphate	2.8E-06	kg
	Sodium (I)	0.03379	kg
	TOC, Total Organic Carbon	0.00091	kg
	Zinc (II)	1.96E-06	kg

TABLE 16 LCI FOR CZ PROCESS INGOT PRODUCTION

	Name	Quantity	Unit
Products	Silicon, single crystal, Czochralski process, photovoltaics {RoW} silicon production, single crystal, Czochralski process, photovoltaics Cut-off, U	1	kg
Materials/fuels	Silicon, solar grade {CN} silicon production, solar grade, modified Siemens process Cut-off, U	1	kg
	Acetic acid, without water, in 98% solution state {GLO} market for acetic acid, without water, in 98% solution state Cut-off, U	0.10797	kg
	Argon, liquid {RER} market for argon, liquid Cut-off, U	1	kg
	Ceramic tile {GLO} market for ceramic tile Cut-off, U	0.167	kg
	Hydrogen fluoride {RoW} market for hydrogen fluoride Cut-off, U	0.001	kg
	Lime, hydrated, packed {RoW} market for lime, hydrated, packed Cut-off, U	0.022	kg
	Nitric acid, without water, in 50% solution state {CN} market for nitric acid, without water, in 50% solution state Cut-off, U	0.0668	kg
	Silicone factory {GLO} market for silicone factory Cut-off, U	1E-11	p
	Sodium hydroxide, without water, in 50% solution state {RoW} market for sodium hydroxide, without water, in 50% solution state Cut-off, U	0.041528	kg
	Water, deionised {RoW} market for water, deionised Cut-off, U	4.01	kg
Resources	Water, cooling, unspecified natural origin, RoW	5.09	m ³
Energy	Electricity, medium voltage {CN} market group for electricity, medium voltage Cut-off, U	32	kWh
	Heat, district or industrial, natural gas {RoW} market for heat, district or industrial, natural gas Cut-off, U	68.2	MJ
Transport	Transport, freight, lorry, unspecified {RoW} market for transport, freight, lorry, unspecified Cut-off, S	1.13	tkm
	Transport, freight train {CN} market for transport, freight	1.41	tkm

	train Cut-off, U		
Emissions to air	Water/m ³ , CN	0.255	m ³
	Heat, waste	115	MJ
	Nitrogen oxides, CN	0.0339	kg
Emissions to water	BOD5 (Biological Oxygen Demand)	0.13	kg
	COD (Chemical Oxygen Demand)	0.13	kg
	DOC, Dissolved Organic Carbon	0.0405	kg
	Hydroxide	0.00442	kg
	Nitrogen, atmospheric	0.009104	kg
	TOC, Total Organic Carbon	0.0405	kg
	Nitrate	0.0835	kg
Waste treatment	Waste, from silicon wafer production, inorganic {RoW} market for waste, from silicon wafer production, inorganic Cut-off, U	0.167	kg
	Sewage sludge (wfr)/RER	4.84	kg

TABLE 17 LCI FOR WAFER PRODUCTION PROCESS

Products	Single-Si wafer, photovoltaic {CN} single-Si wafer production, photovoltaic Cut-off, U	1	m ²
Materials/fuels	Silicon, single crystal, Czochralski process, photovoltaics {RoW} silicon ingot production, single crystal, Czochralski process, photovoltaics Cut-off, U	0.595	kg
	Acetic acid, without water, in 98% solution state {GLO} market for acetic acid, without water, in 98% solution state Cut-off, U	0.039	kg
	Acrylic binder, with water, in 54% solution state {RoW} market for acrylic binder, with water, in 54% solution state Cut-off, U	0.002	kg
	Alkylbenzene sulfonate, linear, petrochemical {GLO} market for alkylbenzene sulfonate, linear, petrochemical Cut-off, U	0.24	kg
	Brass {RoW} market for brass Cut-off, U	0.00745	kg
	Dipropylene glycol monomethyl ether {RoW} market for dipropylene glycol monomethyl ether Cut-off, U	0.3	kg
	Glass wool mat {GLO} market for glass wool mat Cut-off, U	0.01	kg
	Hydrochloric acid, without water, in 30% solution state {RoW} market for hydrochloric acid, without water, in 30% solution state Cut-off, U	0.0027	kg
	Sodium hydroxide, without water, in 50% solution state	0.015	kg

	{RoW} market for sodium hydroxide, without water, in 50% solution state Cut-off, U		
	Steel, chromium steel 18/8, hot rolled {GLO} market for steel, chromium steel 18/8, hot rolled Cut-off, U	0.00151	kg
	Wafer factory {GLO} market for wafer factory Cut-off, U	0.000004	p
	Water, deionised {RoW} market for water, deionised Cut-off, U	55.6	kg
	Wire drawing, steel {GLO} market for wire drawing, steel Cut-off, U	0.00895	kg
Energy	Electricity, medium voltage {CN} market group for electricity, medium voltage Cut-off, U	4.76	kWh
	Heat, district or industrial, natural gas {RoW} market for heat, district or industrial, natural gas Cut-off, U	4	MJ
Transport	Transport, freight, lorry, unspecified {GLO} market group for transport, freight, lorry, unspecified Cut-off, U	0.236	tkm
	Transport, freight train {CN} transport, freight train, diesel Cut-off, U	1.25	tkm
Emissions to air	Water/m3, CN	0.009751	m3
	Heat, waste	17.1	MJ
Emissions to water	AOX, Adsorbable Organic Halogen	0.029555	kg
	BOD5 (Biological Oxygen Demand)	0.029555	kg
	COD (Chemical Oxygen Demand)	0.029555	kg
	DOC, Dissolved Organic Carbon	0.011083	kg
	TOC, Total Organic Carbon	0.011083	kg
Waste treatment	Waste, from silicon wafer production {GLO} market for waste, from silicon wafer production Cut-off, U	0.17	kg
	Wastewater from wafer fabrication {RoW} market for wastewater from wafer fabrication Cut-off, U	0.05	m3

TABLE 18 LCI FOR PERC CELL PRODUCTION

	Name	Quantity	Unit
Products	Photovoltaic PERC cell, single-Si wafer {CN} photovoltaic cell production, single-Si wafer Cut-off, U	1	m ²
Materials/fuels	Single-Si wafer, photovoltaic {CN} single-Si wafer production, photovoltaic Cut-off, U	1.04	m ²
	Metallization paste, front side {CN} metallization paste production, front side Cut-off, U	4080	mg
	Metallization paste, back side {CN} metallization paste production, back side Cut-off, U	1130	mg
	Metallization paste, back side, aluminium {CN}	6680	mg

	metallization paste production, back side, aluminium Cut-off, U		
	Water, deionised {RoW} market for water, deionised Cut-off, U	28.7	kg
	Isopropanol {RoW} market for isopropanol Cut-off, U	0.0131	kg
	Hydrochloric acid, without water, in 30% solution state {RoW} market for hydrochloric acid, without water, in 30% solution state Cut-off, U	0.0141	kg
	Sulfuric acid {RoW} market for sulfuric acid Cut-off, U	0.0588	kg
	Nitric acid, without water, in 50% solution state {CN} market for nitric acid, without water, in 50% solution state Cut-off, U	0.0867	kg
	Phosphoryl chloride {GLO} market for Cut-off, U	0.000181	kg
	Trimethyl aluminium (TMA)	0.000242	kg
	Potassium Hydroxide, 40% solution for PERC cell production (GLO)	0.0516	kg
	Hydrogen fluoride, 49% in solution for photovoltaic PERC cell production {RoW} market for hydrogen fluoride Cut-off, U	0.0802	kg
	Hydrogen peroxide, in 30% solution state {GLO} market for Cut-off, U	1.15	kg
	Nitrogen, liquid {RoW} market for nitrogen, liquid Cut-off, U	3.57E-08	kg
	Silane, at plant (CN)	0.00229	kg
	Ammonia, anhydrous, liquid {CN} market for ammonia, anhydrous, liquid Cut-off, U	1.27E-07	kg
	Oxygen, liquid {RoW} market for oxygen, liquid Cut-off, U	3.15E-09	kg
	Nitrous oxide {GLO} market for nitrous oxide Cut-off, U	1.71E-05	kg
	Biomethane, medium pressure, vehicle grade {RoW} market for biomethane, medium pressure, vehicle grade Cut-off, U	0.00111	kg
	APOLLO Photovoltaic cell factory {CN} photovoltaic cell factory construction Cut-off, U	4E-07	p
Resources	Water, cooling, unspecified natural origin, CN-ECGC	0.232	m3
Energy	Electricity, medium voltage {CN-ECGC} market for electricity, medium voltage Cut-off, U	5.8	kWh
	Compressed air production (CN) Cut-off U	11.67	kg
Transport	Transport, freight, lorry, unspecified {GLO} market group for transport, freight, lorry, unspecified Cut-off, U	0.226	tkm
	Transport, freight train {CN} market for transport, freight train Cut-off, U	1.26	tkm

Emissions to air	Water	3.96	kg
	Hydrogen fluoride	3.04	kg
	Silicon	3.16E-08	kg
	Silver (I)	6.64E-06	kg
	Ammonia, CN	3.07E-05	kg
	Chlorine	0.00248	kg
	Hydrogen	0.011	kg
	Silicon	0.00262	kg
	NMVOOC, non-methane volatile organic compounds, CN	0.0126	kg
Waste treatment	Waste, from silicon wafer production {GLO} market for waste, from silicon wafer production Cut-off, U	2.32	kg
	Wastewater from PV cell production {RoW} market for wastewater from PV cell production Cut-off, U	0.0396	m3
	Spent solvent mixture {RoW} market for spent solvent mixture Cut-off, U	0.172	kg

TABLE 19 LCI FOR SILVER METALLIZATION PASTE FOR FRONTSIDE OF PERC CELLS

	Name	Quantity	Uni
Products	Metallization paste, front side {CN} metallization paste production, front side Cut-off, U	1	kg
Materials/fuels	Chemical, organic {GLO} market for chemical, organic Cut-off, U	0.1212	kg
	Lead {GLO} market for lead Cut-off, U	0.0505	kg
	Silver {GLO} market for silver Cut-off, U	0.8383	kg
	Solder factory {RoW} solder factory construction Cut-off, U	2E-10	p
Energy	Electricity, medium voltage {CN} market group for electricity, medium voltage Cut-off, U	0.25	kWh
	Heat, district or industrial, natural gas {GLO} market group for heat, district or industrial, natural gas Cut-off, U	0.828	MJ
Transport	Transport, freight, lorry, unspecified {RoW} market for transport, freight, lorry, unspecified Cut-off, U	0.101	tkm
	Transport, freight train {CN} market for transport, freight train Cut-off, U	0.606	tkm
Emissions to air	Heat, waste	0.9	MJ

TABLE 20 LCI FOR SILVER METALLIZATION PASTE FOR REAR SIDE OF PERC CELLS

	Name	Quantity	Unit
Products	Metallization paste, back side {CN} metallization paste production, back side Cut-off, U	1	kg
Materials/fuels	Chemical, organic {GLO} market for chemical, organic Cut-off, U	0.2525	kg
	Lead {GLO} market for lead Cut-off, U	0.0808	kg
	Silver {GLO} market for silver Cut-off, U	0.6767	kg
	Solder factory {GLO} market for solder factory Cut-off, U	2E-10	p
Energy	Electricity, medium voltage {CN} market group for electricity, medium voltage Cut-off, S	0.25	kWh
	Heat, district or industrial, natural gas {GLO} market group for heat, district or industrial, natural gas Cut-off, U	0.828	MJ
Transport	Transport, freight, lorry, unspecified {RoW} transport, freight, lorry, all sizes, EURO3 to generic market for transport, freight, lorry, unspecified Cut-off, S	0.101	tkm
	Transport, freight train {CN} market for transport, freight train Cut-off, U	0.606	tkm
Emissions to air	Heat, waste	0.9	MJ

TABLE 21 LCI FOR ALUMINIUM METALLIZATION PASTE

	Name	Quantity	unit
Products	Metallization paste, back side, aluminium {CN} metallization paste production, back side, aluminium Cut-off, U	1	kg
Materials/fuels	Aluminium, wrought alloy {GLO} market for aluminium, wrought alloy Cut-off, U	0.808	kg
	Chemical, organic {GLO} market for chemical, organic Cut-off, U	0.1717	kg
	Silica sand {GLO} market for silica sand Cut-off, U	0.0303	kg
	Solder factory {GLO} market for solder factory Cut-off, U	2E-10	p
Energy	Electricity/heat		
	Electricity, medium voltage {CN} market group for electricity, medium voltage Cut-off, U	0.25	kWh
	Heat, district or industrial, natural gas {GLO} market group for heat, district or industrial, natural gas Cut-off, U	0.828	MJ
Transport	Transport, freight, lorry, unspecified {GLO} market group for transport, freight, lorry, unspecified Cut-off, U	0.101	tkm
	Transport, freight train {CN} market for transport, freight train Cut-off, U	0.606	tkm
Emissions to air	Heat, waste	0.9	MJ

TABLE 22 LCI FOR TRIMETHYL ALUMINIUM (TMA)

	Name	Quantity	unit
Products	APOLLO Trimethyl aluminium (TMA)	1	kg
Materials/fuels	Methylchloride {GLO} market for Cut-off, U	1.05065	kg
	Aluminium, wrought alloy {GLO} market for aluminium, wrought alloy Cut-off, U	0.18714	kg
	Sodium {GLO} market for sodium Cut-off, U	0.476521	kg

TABLE 23 LCI FOR SILANE PRODUCTION

	Name	Quantity	Unit
Product	Silane, at plant (CN)	1	kg
Materials/fuels	Silicon, metallurgical grade (CN) silicon production, metallurgical grade Cut-off, U	1	kg
	Lime, hydrated, packed {RoW} market for lime, hydrated, packed Cut-off, U	0.5	kg
	Silicon tetrachloride {GLO} market for Cut-off, U	0.0814	kg
	Hydrogen, liquid {RER} hydrogen cracking, APME Cut-off, U	8.42	kg
	Nitrogen, liquid {RoW} market for nitrogen, liquid Cut-off, U	6.21	kg
	Silicone factory {GLO} market for silicone factory Cut-off, U	1.03E-11	p
Electricity/heat	Heat, district or industrial, natural gas {GLO} market group for heat, district or industrial, natural gas Cut-off, U	179	MJ
	Electricity, medium voltage {CN} market group for electricity, medium voltage Cut-off, U	25	kWh
Transport	Transport, freight, lorry, unspecified {RER} market for transport, freight, lorry, unspecified Cut-off, U	0.787	tkm
	Transport, freight train {CN} market for transport, freight train Cut-off, U	4.72	tkm
Emissions to air	Heat, waste	90	MJ
Emissions to water	Chloride	0.0385	kg
	Copper, ion	6.85E-07	kg
	Nitrogen	0.000285	kg
	Phosphate, CN	4.3E-06	kg
	Sodium	0.027	kg
	Zinc (II)	1.83E-06	kg
	Iron (II)	1.83E-06	kg
	BOD5 (Biological Oxygen Demand), CN	7.85E-05	kg
	COD (Chemical Oxygen Demand), CN	0.000883	kg
	DOC, Dissolved Organic Carbon	0.000715	kg

	AOX, Adsorbable Organic Halogen	1.08E-05	kg
	Cadmium (II)	9.47E-07	kg
	Chromium, ion	7.87E-07	kg
	Fluoride	3.71E-05	kg
	Lead (II)	2.04E-07	kg
	Mercury (II)	1.86E-09	kg
	Nickel (II)	7.98E-07	kg
	Phosphorous acid	4.65E-07	kg
	Sulfate	0.000186	kg

TABLE 24 LCI FOR PERC PV MODULE PRODUCTION

	Name	Quantity	Unit
Products	Photovoltaic panel, mono-PERC module production {CN} photovoltaic panel production, single-Si wafer Cut-off, U	1	module
Materials/fuels	Photovoltaic PERC cell, single-Si wafer {CN} photovoltaic cell production, single-Si wafer Cut-off, U	1.967083	m ²
	1-propanol {GLO} market for 1-propanol Cut-off, U	0.01769	kg
	Aluminium, extrusion, at plant/kg/RNA	2.586551	kg
	Solar glass, low-iron {GLO} market for solar glass, low-iron Cut-off, U	16.58435	kg
	Copper, cathode {GLO} market for copper, cathode Cut-off, U	0.161931	kg
	Lead {GLO} market for lead Cut-off, U	0.014672	kg
	Tin {GLO} market for tin Cut-off, U	0.021953	kg
	Ethylvinylacetate, foil {GLO} market for ethylvinylacetate, foil Cut-off, U	2.145316	kg
	Polyethylene terephthalate, granulate, amorphous {GLO} market for polyethylene terephthalate, granulate, amorphous Cut-off, U	0.675981	kg
	Polyvinylfluoride, film {GLO} market for polyvinylfluoride, film Cut-off, U	0.098245	kg
	Silicone product {RoW} market for silicone product Cut-off, U	0.247787	kg
	Glass fibre reinforced plastic, polyamide, injection moulded {GLO} market for glass fibre reinforced plastic, polyamide, injection moulded Cut-off, U	0.247787	kg
	Anti-reflex-coating, etching, solar glass {GLO} market for anti-reflex-coating, etching, solar glass Cut-off, U	2.156183	m ²
	Corrugated board box {RoW} market for corrugated board box Cut-off, U	0.530352	kg

	Polystyrene, expandable {GLO} market for polystyrene, expandable Cut-off, U	0.045645	kg
	EUR-flat pallet {RoW} market for EUR-flat pallet Cut-off, U	0.025126	p
Electricity/heat	Electricity, medium voltage {CN-ECGC} market for electricity, medium voltage Cut-off, U	8.976852	kWh
	Photovoltaic panel factory {GLO} market for photovoltaic panel factory Cut-off, U	8.78E-06	p
Resource	Tap water {GLO} market group for tap water Cut-off, U	1.519327	kg
Transport	Transport, freight train {CN} market for transport, freight train Cut-off, U	3.60813	tkm
	Transport, freight, lorry, unspecified {RoW} market for transport, freight, lorry, unspecified Cut-off, U	6.020794	tkm
Waste treatment	Waste plastic, mixture {RoW} market for waste plastic, mixture Cut-off, U	0.009499	kg
	Waste, from silicon wafer production {GLO} market for waste, from silicon wafer production Cut-off, U	0.007651	kg

TABLE 25 LCI FOR DISTRIBUTION OF PV MODULE TO EUROPE FROM CHINA

	Name	Quantity	Unit
Process	Transport - China to Europe for 1 PV module	1	p
Transport	Transport, freight, lorry >32 metric ton, EURO5 {RoW} transport, freight, lorry >32 metric ton, EURO5 Cut-off, U	7.08	tkm
	Transport, freight, lorry >32 metric ton, EURO5 {RER} transport, freight, lorry >32 metric ton, EURO5 Cut-off, U	18.88	tkm
	Transport, freight, sea, container ship {GLO} market for transport, freight, sea, container ship Cut-off, U	472	tkm

TABLE 26 LCI FOR TRANSPORT OF WASTE PV MODULE FROM SITE OF USE TO RECYCLING PLANT VIA COLLECTION FACILITY

	Name	Quantity	Unit
Process	Transport Waste PERC PV module to recycling	1	p
Transport	Transport, freight, lorry 16-32 metric ton, EURO5 {RER} market for transport, freight, lorry 16-32 metric ton, EURO5 Cut-off, U	2.36	tkm
	Transport, freight, lorry 16-32 metric ton, EURO5 {RER} market for transport, freight, lorry 16-32 metric ton, EURO5 Cut-off, U	11.8	tkm

TABLE 27 LCI FOR RECYCLING OF PERC MODULE

	Name	Quantity	Unit
Process	PV PERC module recycling [DE]	1	p
Fuels	Diesel {RER} market group for diesel Cut-off, U	0.049	kg
	Natural gas, liquefied {GLO} market for natural gas, liquefied Cut-off, U	0.000874	m3
Energy	Electricity, medium voltage {RER} market group for electricity, medium voltage Cut-off, U	1.416	kWh
Waste treatment	Waste, electrical and electronic cables {RoW} market for waste, electrical and electronic cables Cut-off, U	0.1534	kg
	Waste aluminium {CH} market for waste aluminium Cut-off, U	2.714	kg
	Waste electric and electronic equipment {GLO} market for waste electric and electronic equipment Cut-off, U	0.0826	kg
	Scrap steel {Europe without Switzerland} market for scrap steel Cut-off, U	0.0472	kg
	Scrap copper {Europe without Switzerland} market for scrap copper Cut-off, U	0.2832	kg
	Waste plastic, consumer electronics {GLO} treatment of waste plastic, consumer electronics, municipal incineration Cut-off, U	3.304	kg
	Waste glass {DE} market for waste glass Cut-off, U	15.104	kg
	Residue from shredder fraction from manual dismantling {GLO} treatment of residue from shredder fraction from manual dismantling, municipal incineration Cut-off, U	1.5576	kg
	Inert waste, for final disposal {RoW} treatment of inert waste, inert material landfill Cut-off, U	0.354	kg

TABLE 28 CRADLE-TO-GRAVE LCI FOR PERC MODULE MANUFACTURED IN CHINA AND TRANSPORTED FOR USE AND RECYCLING IN EUROPE

	Name	Quantity	Unit
Products	PERC module cradle to grave	23.6	kg
Production	Photovoltaic panel, mono-PERC module production {CN photovoltaic panel production, single-Si wafer Cut-off, U	23.6	kg
Distribution	APOLLO Distribution of PV module to Europe from CN	1	p
Collection & Waste Treatment	Transport Waste PERC PV module to recycling	1	p
	PV PERC module recycling [DE]	1	p

10. Annex 2 – SLCA supporting information

TABLE 29 SOCIAL IMPACT INDICATORS FOR STAKEHOLDER GROUPS

Workers	Local communities	Value chain actors	Consumers & society
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Forced labour • Child labour • Gender equity in participation • Gender equity in leadership • Gender wage equity • Reproductive toxicity • Occupational injury & safety • Access to social security/benefits • Freedom of association 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Land rights & displacement • Community health impacts • Access to grievance mechanisms 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Corruption & transparency risks • Freedom of association 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Corruption & transparency risks • Freedom of association

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